

1. Dry matter yield and grain yield of 57 F₁ hybrids and 43 inbreds with different growth durations, IRRI, 1988 dry season. Vertical lines represent the standard error of the mean.

2. Harvest index of F₁ hybrids and inbreds with different growth durations, IRRI, 1988 DS. Vertical lines represent the standard error of the mean.

slightly lower yield by very short-duration entries. F₁ hybrids and inbreds with growth durations of 125-129 d had the highest grain yield.

The increase in biomass with growth duration and the almost constant grain yield regardless of growth duration resulted in higher HI in short-duration

cultivars (Fig. 2). F₁ hybrids showed an average 10% advantage in HI over inbreds. (HI higher than 0.50 is often observed in short-duration F₁ hybrids.)

F₁ hybrids, regardless of duration, showed heterosis for total dry weight production and HI, with greatly increased grain yields. □

Effect of stem thickness and carbohydrate content on ratoon rice yield

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We studied the effect of stem thickness and carbohydrate content on yield of ratoon rice in 1984-85 and 1985-86. Varieties were Bhavani, Ponni, and IR20, in a randomized block design with three replications. The main crops were cultivated according to recommended practices.

Stem thickness of the ratoons was measured with a screw-gauge at harvest of the main crop. Carbohydrate content of the stubble was estimated immediately after harvest by the method suggested by Somogyi, using the Spectronic-20 colorimeter.

In both years, Bhavani had significantly higher ratoon crop grain yield (see table). Its stem thickness was also significantly higher than that of the two other varieties. Bhavani also had the highest carbohydrate content in the stubble. This could have induced more vigorous regeneration of ratoon tillers, resulting in the production of a larger number of tillers and higher grain yield. □

Stem thickness, carbohydrate content, and ratoon rice yield.

Variety	1984-85			1985-86		
	Stem thickness (mm)	Carbohydrate content (%)	Ratoon grain yield (t/ha)	Stem thickness (mm)	Carbohydrate content (%)	Ratoon grain yield (t/ha)
Bhavani	3.5	8.9	1.6	3.1	8.8	2.9
Ponni	2.8	7.8	1.0	2.7	7.9	1.3
IR20	2.8	7.6	0.3	2.8	7.6	0.3
LSD (0.05)	0.5	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.7	0.2

Variation in rice hull weights

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One way to further improve rice yields in the tropics is to increase the harvest index (HI) — the ratio of grain weight to biomass. (Wheat shows higher HI than rice, whose hull weight is substantially heavier than wheat chaff.) Reducing the partitioning of dry weight to the hull could be an approach to improving HI.

We examined seasonal variations in hull weight. Early-maturing IR58 and medium-maturing IR29723-143-3-2-1 were transplanted each month for 1 yr. Spacing was 20 × 20 cm, fertilizer was 120 kg N/ha. Filled grains (1.06 specific gravity) of each harvest were separated by salt solution and dried at 80°C for 5 d. Three 200-seed samples per transplanting month were dehulled manually, redried for 24 h, and hull and kernel weight determined. Grains of 10 different cultivars were dehulled for comparison.